

Bronze Hessian Structure and Kaehler-Norden Manifolds¹

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Abstract

In this paper, we investigated the locally decomposable Bronze-Hessian manifolds and holomorphic Bronze Norden Hessian manifolds. We investigate that if the smooth function $f:M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is decomposable, then the triplet $(M, \Psi, \nabla^2 f)$ is a locally decomposable Bronze Hessian manifold, where Ψ is a Bronze structure and ∇ represents the Levi-Civita Connection of g . We obtain some conditions under which the manifold M associated with Hessian metric h and complex Bronze structure. Moreover, we investigate twin Norden Silver Hessian metric for a Kaehler-Norden Bronze Hessian manifold.

Keywords

Bronze Structure, Pure Tensor, Hessian Metric, Decomposable and Holomorphic Tensors.

Introduction

Crasmareanu et al. explored the geometry of the Golden structure, inspired by the golden ratio. Building on this motivation, Crasmareanu introduced the concept of a Golden structure and investigated various properties of Riemannian manifolds associated with it [6, 17]. Primo et al. [3] examined several algebraic and geometric characterizations of the silver ratio. Pandey and Sameer [25] investigated the bronze structure and connections as bronze structure, integrability, and bronze Riemannian manifolds.

Gezer et al. [1] explored the integrability conditions and curvature characteristics of Golden Riemannian structures involving the ϕ -operator. They also investigated intriguing properties of twin Golden Riemannian metrics, providing several examples. In [2], Gezer et al. examined the properties of Riemannian manifolds equipped with the Hessian metric h and a complex golden structure. Additionally, in [5], Salimov and Gezer demonstrated that Kaehler manifolds admit a Norden-Hessian

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metric when the function f is holomorphic, and they provided conditions for para-Kaehler structures in the context of Norden-Hessian metrics.

In [11], Shima first introduced the concept of the Hessian metrics. Udriste et al. [7], defined the Hessian metric on a pseudo-Riemannian manifold and is given by $h = \nabla^2 f$, where ∇ is the Levi-Civita connection of g and $f: M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a smooth function. Bercu et al. studied Hessian metrics and some of its applications in [8, 9, 10]. They also derived systems of the Partial differential equations systems which are produced by two connections, one determined by a pseudo-Riemannian metric g and other determined by pseudo-Riemannian Hessian metrics h . Shima studied the geometry of the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^n associated with the Hessian Riemannian metrics in [12]. Furthermore, Hessian metrics have been investigated by numerous researchers [5, 7, 13, 14, 20], highlighting their broad interest and applicability in differential geometry.

In [20], Kumar introduced the concept of n^{th} order Hessian structures on manifolds and studied in detail for third-order ($n = 3$). He deduced a one-to-one correspondence between a certain class of connections and third-order Hessian structures on the second-order tangent bundle of a manifold. Additionally, Kumar provided a geometric characterization of symmetric third-order Hessian structures. Iscan et al. [19] investigated the geometry of Kaehler-Norden manifolds. Iscan and Salimov used the Tachibana operators and studied properties of curvature scalars and Riemannian curvature tensors of Kaehler-Norden manifolds.

The notion of the polynomial structure on a manifold was introduced by Goldberg and Yano [21] in 1970. Let M represents the C^∞ -differentiable real manifold. If P satisfies the following algebraic equation

$$Q(P) = P^n + a_n P^{n-1} + \dots + a_2 P + a_1 I = 0,$$

then, a (1,1)-tensor field P is called a polynomial structure of degree n and P has constant rank on M . Here I denote identity tensor field of type (1,1) and a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n are real numbers.

Motivated by the research work of above authors, we have investigated locally decomposable Bronze-Hessian manifolds and holomorphic Bronze Norden Hessian manifolds. We show that if the function f is decomposable, then the triplet $(M, \Psi, \nabla^2 f)$ is a locally decomposable Bronze Hessian manifold. Furthermore, we have derived conditions under which the manifold M equipped with Hessian metric h and complex Bronze structure, satisfies the desired properties.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we have ϕ_ψ -Operator and some definitions.

Let ψ denotes a tensor field of type (1,1) and M represents the n -dimensional manifold. The tensor field t of type (r, s) satisfying the following condition

$$\begin{aligned} t(\psi U_1, U_2, \dots, U_s; \xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_r) &= t(U_1, \psi U_2, \dots, U_s; \xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_r) \\ &\quad \vdots \\ &= t(U_1, U_2, \dots, \psi U_s; \xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_r) \\ &= t(U_1, U_2, \dots, U_s; \psi \xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_r) \\ &\quad \vdots \\ &= t(U_1, U_2, \dots, U_s; \xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \psi \xi_r) \end{aligned}$$

for any $U_1, U_2, \dots, U_s \in \mathfrak{S}_0^1(M)$ and $\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_r \in \mathfrak{S}_1^0(M)$ is a said to be pure tensor field associated with ψ , where $'\psi$ is the adjoint operator of ψ and it is defined by

$$('\psi\xi)(U) = \xi(\psi U) = (\xi \circ \psi)(U).$$

Now, consider an operator

$$\phi_\psi: \mathfrak{S}_s^0(M) \rightarrow \mathfrak{S}_{s+1}^0(M)$$

applied on the pure tensor field t of type $(0, s)$ associated with ψ by

$$\begin{aligned} (\phi_\psi t)(U, V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s) &= (\psi U)(t(V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s)) \\ &\quad - U(t(\psi V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s)) \\ &\quad + t((L_{V_1}\psi)U, V_2, \dots, V_s) \\ &\quad \dots \\ &\quad + t(V_1, V_2, \dots, (L_{V_s}\psi)U) \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

for any $U, V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s \in \mathfrak{S}_0^1(M)$, where L_V denotes the Lie differentiation with respect to V . The pure tensor t is said to be ϕ -tensor if $\phi_\psi t = 0$. If ψ is a product structure, then a ϕ -tensor is said to be a decomposable tensor. A ϕ -tensor is called an analytic tensor if ψ is a complex structure [15, 22].

3. Locally Decomposable Bronze-Hessian Structure

Let M is an n -dimensional differentiable manifold and Ψ be a tensor field of type $(1,1)$ on M . If it satisfying the condition

$$\Psi^2 - 3\Psi - I = 0 \tag{3.1}$$

then, the structure Ψ is called Bronze structure and the pair (M, Ψ) is called a Bronze manifold [25].

Let g be a Riemannian metric on differentiable manifold M and (M, g) is a Riemannian manifold equipped with the Bronze structure Ψ such that

$$g(\Psi U, V) = g(U, \Psi V), \tag{3.2}$$

for any vector fields U and V on M .

Let F represents the almost product structure. Suppose Riemannian metric g and differentiable manifold M associated with a tensor field F of type $(1,1)$, satisfying the following conditions

$$g(FU, V) = g(U, FV),$$

and

$$F^2 = I, \quad \nabla F = 0,$$

where ∇ is the Levi-Civita connection of g . This type of manifold is called a locally decomposable Riemannian manifold.

Suppose F induces a Bronze structure on manifold M as follows

$$\Psi = \frac{1}{2}(I \mp \sqrt{13}F). \tag{3.3}$$

Conversely, the Bronze structure yields an almost product structure as

$$F = \mp \frac{1}{\sqrt{13}}(2\Psi - 3I). \tag{3.4}$$

Theorem 3.1 Let (M, Ψ, g) is a Bronze Riemannian manifold. The Ψ is said to be integrable, if $\phi_\psi g = 0$.

Proof. From (3.2) and $\nabla g = 0$, it follows that

$$g(U, (\nabla_W \Psi)V) = g((\nabla_W \Psi)U, V), \tag{3.5}$$

where $U, V, W \in M$.

Now, using (3.5) and $[U, V] = \nabla_U V - \nabla_V U$, the equation (2.1) can be transform as

$$(\phi_\Psi g)(U, V, W) = -g((\nabla_U \Psi)V, W) + g((\nabla_V \Psi)U, W) + g(V, (\nabla_W \Psi)U). \quad (3.6)$$

Similarly, we obtain

$$(\phi_\Psi g)(W, V, U) = -g((\nabla_W \Psi)V, U) + g((\nabla_V \Psi)W, U) + g(V, (\nabla_U \Psi)W). \quad (3.7)$$

Adding (3.6) and (3.7), we have

$$(\phi_\Psi g)(U, V, W) + (\phi_\Psi g)(W, V, U) = 2g(U, (\nabla_V \Psi)W). \quad (3.8)$$

Now, putting $\phi_\Psi g = 0$ in (3.8), we get $\nabla \Psi = 0$.

Corollary 3.1 *Let (M, Ψ, g) be a Bronze Riemannian manifold and ∇ be the Levi-Civita connection of g . The condition $\phi_\Psi g = 0$ is equivalent to $\nabla \Psi = 0$.*

If a Riemannian metric g is pure with respect to Bronze structure, then it is also pure with respect to the almost product structure F . A straightforward computation by using equation (3.4) yields

$$\phi_F g = \frac{1}{\sqrt{13}} \phi_\Psi g. \quad (3.9)$$

For an almost product Riemannian manifold, Salimov et al. [4] shown that the almost product structure F is integrable, if $\phi_F g = 0$. Therefore, by the Theorem 3.1 and equation (3.9), it follows that

Proposition 3.1 *Suppose F be an almost product structure of a Bronze Riemannian manifold (M, Ψ, g) . The Bronze structure Ψ is integrable if $\phi_F g = 0$.*

A Bronze Riemannian manifold (M, Ψ, g) with an integrable Bronze structure Ψ is called a locally Bronze Riemannian manifold. If the metric g of the locally Bronze Riemannian manifold takes the following form

$$ds^2 = g_{xy}(\xi^z) d\xi^x d\xi^y + g_{\bar{x}\bar{y}}(\xi^{\bar{z}}) d\xi^{\bar{x}} d\xi^{\bar{y}},$$

then, M is known as locally decomposable Bronze Riemannian manifold. Where $x, y, z = 1, 2, \dots, m$, $\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z} = m + 1, m + 2, \dots, n$, and g_{xy} are functions of ξ^z only, $g_{x\bar{y}} = 0$ and $g_{\bar{x}\bar{y}}$ are the functions of $\xi^{\bar{z}}$ only. On the other hand, the almost product structure F is said to be covariantly constant with respect to the Levi-Civita connection of g if and only if the locally product Riemannian manifold associated with F is locally decomposable [16].

Salimov et al. showed that the condition $\phi_F g = 0$ is equivalent to $\nabla F = 0$ in [4]. Therefore, we have the following result:

Proposition 3.2 *Let F be an almost product structure of a Bronze Riemannian manifold (M, Ψ, g) . The manifold M is a locally decomposable Bronze Riemannian manifold if and only if $\phi_F g = 0$.*

Theorem 3.2 *Let f is a smooth function such that the Hessian $\nabla^2 f$ is non-degenerate and (M, F, g) denote the locally decomposable Riemannian manifold, where ∇ be the Levi-Civita connection of g . The triplet $(M, \Psi, h = \nabla^2 f)$ is a locally decomposable Bronze Hessian manifold, if the smooth function f is decomposable, i.e. $\phi_F(df) = 0$, where Ψ be the Bronze structure related with the almost product structure.*

Proof. Suppose f is a decomposable function on (M, F, g) that is $\phi_F(df) = 0$.

Then, form (2.1) and (3.3), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 &= (\phi_F(df))(U, V) \\
 &= (FU)((df)(V)) - U((df)(FV)) + (df)((L_V F)(X)) \\
 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\Psi(U)((df)(V)) - U((df)(\Psi V)) + (df)([V, \Psi U]) - (df)\Psi([V, U])] \\
 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\Psi(U)((df)(V)) - U((df)(\Psi V)) + (df)(\nabla_V \Psi U - \nabla_{\Psi U} V - \Psi(\nabla_V U - \nabla_U V)) \\
 &\quad (df)(-\nabla_U \Psi V + \nabla_U \Psi V)] \\
 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [(\nabla_{\Psi U} df)(V) + (\nabla_U df)(\Psi V) - (df)(\nabla \Psi)(V, U) + (df)(\nabla \Psi)(U, V)]
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.10}$$

From (3.4), it follows that $\nabla F = 0$ is a equivalent to $\nabla \Psi = 0$. Then, the equation (3.10) becomes

$$(\nabla^2 f)(V, \Psi U) = (\nabla^2 f)(\Psi V, U). \tag{3.11}$$

Therefore, the triplet $(M, \Psi, h = \nabla^2 f)$ is called a Bronze Hessian manifold.

Now applying ϕ_Ψ -operator to the Hessian metric h , we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\phi_\Psi h)(U, V, W) &= \Psi(U)(h(V, W)) - U(h(\Psi V, W)) - h(\nabla_{\Psi U} V, W) \\
 &\quad + h((\nabla \Psi)(U, V)W) + h(V, (\nabla \Psi)(U, W)) - h(V, \nabla_{\Psi U} W) \\
 &\quad + h(\Psi(\nabla_U V), W) + h(\Psi V, \nabla_U W) \\
 &= (\nabla_{\Psi U} h)(V, W) - (\nabla_U h)(\Psi V, W) + h((\nabla \Psi)(U, V), W) \\
 &\quad + h(V, (\nabla \Psi)(U, W))
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.12}$$

Putting $h(V, W) = (\nabla_V \nabla_W f)$ and $\nabla \Psi = 0$ in (3.12), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\phi_\Psi h)(U, V, W) &= (\phi_\Psi h)(U, W, V) \\
 &= (\nabla_{\Psi U} (\nabla^2 f))(W, V) - (\nabla_U (\nabla^2 f))(W, \Psi V) \\
 &= (\nabla^3 f)(W, V, \Psi U) - (\nabla^3 f)(W, \Psi V, U)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.13}$$

The equation (3.11) yields

$$(\nabla^3 f)(\Psi U, V, W) = (\nabla^3 f)(U, \Psi V, W) \tag{3.14}$$

Now using Ricci identity, then from (3.14), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\nabla^3 f)(\Psi U, V, W) &= \nabla_W (\nabla_V (\nabla_{\Psi U} f)) \\
 &= \nabla_V (\nabla_W (\nabla_{\Psi U} f)) - (df)(R(W, V)\Psi U) \\
 &= (\nabla^3 f)(\Psi U, W, V) - (df)(R(W, V)\Psi U)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.15}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\nabla^3 f)(U, \Psi V, W) &= \nabla_W (\nabla_{\Psi V} (\nabla_U f)) \\
 &= \nabla_{\Psi V} (\nabla_W (\nabla_U f)) - (df)(R(W, \Psi V)U) \\
 &= (\nabla^3 f)(U, W, \Psi V) - (df)(R(W, \Psi V)U)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.16}$$

In (M, F, g) , the curvature tensor R of g is totally pure and Hessian metric h is symmetric. So that curvature tensor R of g is totally pure endowed with the Bronze structure Ψ . Thus, from (3.15) and (3.16), we have

$$(\nabla^3 f)(W, \Psi U, V) = (\nabla^3 f)(W, U, \Psi V), \tag{3.17}$$

that is, the tensor field $\nabla^3 f$ is totally pure with Bronze structure Ψ . Thus, we have a higher-order Hessian structure $\nabla^3 f$ on manifold M as given in the [20]. From (3.13) and (3.17), we obtain the following: $\phi_\Psi h = 0$.

Analogous to [2, 23], we have the following example.

Example 3.1 Let g be a Euclidean metric, that is

$$g = \begin{pmatrix} \delta_j^i & 0 \\ 0 & \delta_{\bar{j}}^{\bar{i}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.18)$$

where $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, k, \bar{i}, \bar{j} = k + 1, k + 2, \dots, n$, associated with the positive orthant \mathbb{R}_+^n , i.e., $\mathbb{R}_+^n = \{u = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n: u_1 > 0, \dots, u_n > 0\}$

The canonical product structure on positive orthant \mathbb{R}_+^n is given by

$$F = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \delta_j^i \\ \delta_{\bar{j}}^{\bar{i}} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.19)$$

where $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, k, \bar{i}, \bar{j} = k + 1, k + 2, \dots, n$.

Then, the triplet (\mathbb{R}_+^n, F, g) is called the locally decomposable Euclidean space. The Bronze structure Ψ on \mathbb{R}_+^n obtained from canonical product structure F are as follows:

$$\Psi = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{3}{2}\delta_j^i & \sqrt{13}\delta_j^i \\ \sqrt{13}\delta_{\bar{j}}^{\bar{i}} & \frac{3}{2}\delta_{\bar{j}}^{\bar{i}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.20)$$

where $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, k, \bar{i}, \bar{j} = k + 1, k + 2, \dots, n$.

Also, the triplet $(\mathbb{R}_+^n, \Psi, g)$ is a locally decomposable Bronze Euclidean space.

Since, the condition $\phi_F(df) = 0$ is locally represented as follows:

$$(\Psi_F df)_{ij} = F_i^m \partial_m \partial_j f - \partial_i (F_j^m \partial_m f) + (\partial_j F_i^m) \partial_m f = 0. \quad (3.21)$$

Now, the function $f: \mathbb{R}_+^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of the following form

$$f(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n) = f_1(u_1) + f_2(u_2) + \dots + f_n(u_n), \quad (3.22)$$

where the differentiable function $f_i: \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a decomposable function and it satisfies $f_i'' > 0$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Now, by putting (3.19) and (3.22) into equation (3.21). Then, equation (3.21) is satisfied.

Hence, the positive definite Hessian is given by

$$\nabla_g^2 f(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 f_1(u_1)}{\partial u_1 \partial u_1} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & \frac{\partial^2 f_n(u_n)}{\partial u_n \partial u_n} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.23)$$

Therefore, $(\mathbb{R}_+^n, \nabla_g^2 f)$ is said to be Riemannian manifold and $\nabla_g^2 f$ is pure endowed with the Bronze structure Ψ . The components of $(\phi_\Psi \nabla_g^2 f)$ can be represented as $(\phi_\Psi \nabla_g^2 f)_{kij} = \Psi_k^m \partial_m (\nabla_g^2 f)_{ij} -$

$$\Psi_i^m \partial_k (\nabla_g^2 f)_{mj} + (\nabla_g^2 f)_{mj} (\partial_i \Psi_k^m - \partial_k \Psi_i^m) + (\nabla_g^2 f)_{im} \partial_j \Psi_k^m \quad (3.24)$$

Now, from (3.20), (3.23) and (3.24), we get $\phi_\Psi \nabla_g^2 f = 0$.

Hence, $(\mathbb{R}_+^n, \Psi, \nabla_g^2 f)$ is known as locally decomposable Bronze Hessian Euclidean space.

Some particular cases:

Case 1. Consider the function $f: \mathbb{R}_+^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of the form

$$f(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n) = e^{u_1} + e^{u_2} + \dots + e^{u_n}.$$

Then, the following Hessian structure is a Riemannian metric.

$$\nabla_g^2 f(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n) = \begin{pmatrix} e^{u_1} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & e^{u_n} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.25)$$

Case 2. Now choosing the Shanon entropy [24] function $f: \mathbb{R}_+^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and is given by $f(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n) =$

$$-\frac{1}{k^2} (\ln k^2 u_1 + \ln k^2 u_2 + \dots + \ln k^2 u_n).$$

Then, the Riemannian metric is given by

$$\nabla_g^2 f(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{k^2(u_1)^2} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & \frac{1}{k^2(u_n)^2} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.26)$$

Therefore, $(\mathbb{R}_+^n, \Psi, \nabla_g^2 f)$ are locally decomposable Bronze Hessian Euclidean space for above two cases.

4. Holomorphic Bronze Norden Hessian Manifold

Let M is an $2n$ -dimensional manifold and Ψ_c be a tensor field of type $(1,1)$ on M^{2n} . The structure Ψ_c is said to be almost complex Bronze structure if Ψ_c satisfying the condition

$$\Psi_c^2 - 3\Psi_c + \frac{11}{2}I = 0, \quad (4.1)$$

The pair (M^{2n}, Ψ_c) is said to be an almost complex Bronze manifold.

Since, the integrability of almost complex Bronze structure Ψ_c is equivalent to the vanishing of the Nijenhuis tensor N_{Ψ_c} . The structure Ψ_c is called integrable if and only if it is possible to establish a torsion-free affine connection ∇ associated with the structure tensor Ψ_c is covariantly constant.

Let Ψ is an almost complex structure on M^{2n} , then

$$\Psi_c = \frac{1}{2} (3I \mp \sqrt{13}\psi) \quad (4.2)$$

is said to be an almost complex Bronze structure on M^{2n} . In fact,

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_c^2 &= \frac{(9I \mp 6\sqrt{13}\psi - 13I)}{2} = \frac{1}{4} \left(-9I \mp 6\sqrt{13} \left(\frac{2\Psi_c - 3I}{\mp\sqrt{13}} \right) \right) \\ &= 3\Psi_c - \frac{22}{4}I. \end{aligned}$$

Conversely, let Ψ_c be an almost complex Bronze structure on M^{2n} , then the structure

$\psi = \mp \frac{1}{\sqrt{13}} (2\Psi_c - 3I)$ is an almost complex structure.

$$\psi^2 = \frac{4(\Psi_c^2 - 3\Psi_c) + 9I}{13} = \frac{-22I + 9I}{13} = -I. \quad (4.3)$$

Let (M^{2n}, g) denotes the pseudo-Riemannian manifold associated with an almost complex structure ψ . If the pseudo-Riemannian metric g is pure associated with almost complex structure ψ , i.e.,

$$g(\psi U, V) = g(U, \psi V),$$

where $U, V \in M$. The pair (M^{2n}, g) is called an almost complex Norden manifold and M is called as Norden manifold if ψ is integrable.

Let Ψ_c be the almost complex Bronze structure associated with pseudo-Riemannian manifold (M^{2n}, g) satisfies the following condition

$$g(\Psi_c U, V) = g(U, \Psi_c V), \quad (4.4)$$

where $U, V \in M$, then the triplet (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) is called an almost complex Norden Bronze manifold.

Hence, for almost complex Norden Bronze manifold (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) , we get

$$g(\Psi_c U, \Psi_c V) = 3g(\Psi_c U, V) - \frac{11}{2}g(U, V). \quad (4.5)$$

In [18], it is given that $\phi_\psi g = 0$ i.e., g is holomorphic, if and only if the almost complex Norden manifold is a holomorphic Norden, i.e., $\nabla\psi = 0$, where ∇ be the Levi-Civita connection of g . Then, (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) is said to be holomorphic Norden manifold if (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) is a Norden manifold associated with holomorphic Norden metric g .

The ϕ -operator method can be used for almost complex Bronze structures in the study of almost complex structure, because the almost complex structure ψ is interrelated to the almost complex Bronze structure Ψ_c . Thus, for the integrability of Ψ_c on pseudo-Riemannian manifolds, another possible condition is obtain by the following:

Theorem 4.1 *Let (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) is an almost complex Bronze Norden manifold and ∇ be the Levi-Civita connection of g . Then*

- (i) Ψ_c is integrable if $\phi_{\Psi_c} g = 0$,
- (ii) the condition $\phi_{\Psi_c} g = 0$ is equivalent to $\nabla\Psi_c = 0$.

Proof. Proof of the theorem is similar to the theorem 3.1

If g is pure with respect to an almost complex Bronze structure Ψ_c , then g is pure with the almost complex structure ψ . From equation (4.2), we get

$$\phi_{\Psi_c} g = \sqrt{13}\phi_\psi g \tag{4.6}$$

As a consequence of the above equality and Theorem 4.1, we obtain the following proposition.

Proposition 4.1 *Let ψ be the almost complex structure of almost complex Bronze Norden manifold (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) . The almost complex Bronze structure Ψ_c is integrable if $\phi_\psi g = 0$.*

Since $\phi_\psi g = 0$ is equivalent to $\nabla\psi = 0$, we get

Proposition 4.2 *Let (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) is an almost complex Bronze Norden manifold and ψ be its corresponding almost complex structure. The triplet (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) is a holomorphic Bronze Norden manifold if and only if $\phi_\psi g = 0$.*

In holomorphic Norden manifold (M^{2n}, ψ, g) , f be a holomorphic function, i.e., $\phi_\psi(df) = 0$. For this instance, repeating the procedure of Theorem 3.2 for the almost complex Bronze structure Ψ_c , by the above proposition and equation (4.6), we get

Proposition 4.3 *Let f is a smooth function with non-degenerate Hessian $\nabla^2 f$, where ∇ denote the Levi-Civita connection of g and (M^{2n}, ψ, g) be a holomorphic Norden manifold. Suppose the structure Ψ_c related with the almost complex structure ψ be an almost complex Bronze structure. Then, the triplet $(M^{2n}, \Psi_c, \nabla^2 f = h)$ is said to be a holomorphic Bronze Norden Hessian manifold, if the smooth function f is holomorphic.*

5. Kaehler-Norden Bronze Hessian Manifolds

Let \tilde{g} be a twin Norden Bronze metric for an almost complex Norden Bronze manifold (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) , given by

$$\tilde{g}(U, V) = (g \circ \Psi_c)(U, V) = g(\Psi_c U, V). \tag{5.1}$$

Obviously $\tilde{g}(\Psi_c U, V) = \tilde{g}(U, \Psi_c V)$, where U, V are the vector fields on M . It should be noted that both the metrics g and \tilde{g} are necessarily of signature (n, n) .

Furthermore, by equation (4.5), we can write

$$\tilde{g}(U, \Psi_c V) = 3\tilde{g}(U, V) - \frac{11}{2}g(U, V). \quad (5.2)$$

Let ∇ and $\tilde{\nabla}$ are the Levi-Civita connections of pseudo-Riemannian metrics g and \tilde{g} , respectively.

Then the potential tensor $Q \in \mathfrak{S}_2^1(M)$ of $\tilde{\nabla}$ associated with ∇ is given by

$$Q(U, V) = \tilde{\nabla}_U V - \nabla_U V. \quad (5.3)$$

The potential tensor Q is symmetric because both the connections are torsion free, i.e.,

$$Q(U, V) = Q(V, U),$$

for any vector fields $U, V \in M$. Now the corresponding (0,3)-tensor field associated with g is defined as

$$Q(U, V, W) = g(Q(U, V), W).$$

Now, for an almost complex Norden Bronze manifold (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) , the tensor field F of type (0,3) is defined by

$$F(U, V, W) = (\nabla_U \tilde{g})(V, W) = g((\nabla_U \Psi_c)V, W), \quad (5.4)$$

which satisfies the following properties

$$\begin{cases} F(U, V, W) = F(U, W, V) \\ F(U, \Psi_c V, \Psi_c W) = -2F(U, V, \Psi_c W) + \frac{11}{2}F(U, V, W) \end{cases} \quad (5.5)$$

The triplet (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) be a Kaehler-Norden Bronze manifold if and only if $F(U, V, W) = 0$ or equivalently $\nabla \Psi_c = 0$.

Let U, V and W be any vector fields on (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) , then making use of equation (5.3), we obtain

$$(\nabla_U \tilde{g})(V, W) = (\tilde{\nabla}_U \tilde{g})(V, W) + \tilde{g}(Q(U, V), W) + \tilde{g}(Q(U, W), V)$$

Now, using equation (5.4) and $\tilde{\nabla}$ be a Levi-Civita connection of \tilde{g} , we get

$$F(U, V, W) = \tilde{g}(Q(U, V), W) + \tilde{g}(Q(U, W), V)$$

Further using equation (5.5) it follows that

$$\tilde{g}(Q(U, V), W) = \frac{1}{2}[F(U, V, W) + F(V, W, U) - F(W, U, V)] \quad (5.6)$$

Replacing W by $\Psi_c W$ and then making use of equations (5.2) and (5.6), we obtain the relation between Q and F as given below:

$$\begin{aligned} Q(U, V, W) &= \frac{3}{11}F(U, V, W) - \frac{1}{11}F(U, V, \Psi_c W) + \frac{3}{11}F(V, W, U) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{11}F(V, \Psi_c W, U) - \frac{3}{11}F(W, U, V) + \frac{1}{11}F(\Psi_c W, U, V) \end{aligned} \quad (5.7)$$

Remark 5.1 Let (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) is a Kaehler-Norden Bronze manifold then the tensor F vanishes and from equation (5.7), the potential tensor Q of $\tilde{\nabla}$ with ∇ also vanishes. Thus, the Levi-Civita connections of g and \tilde{g} coincide, i.e., $\tilde{\nabla} = \nabla$ if (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) is a Kaehler-Norden Bronze manifold.

Theorem 5.1. The almost complex Bronze structure Ψ_c is an isomorphism on the tangent space $T_u M$ of the manifold M , for every $u \in M$

Proof: Let $U \in \ker \Psi_c$, then $\Psi_c U = 0$ and this implies $\Psi_c^2 U = 0$. Thus, from (4.1) we have $U = 0$ i.e. $\ker \Psi_c = 0$. Therefore, Ψ_c becomes an isomorphism on $T_u M$.

Suppose g be a metric tensor associated with Riemannian manifold (M^{2n}, g) . The gradient $grad(f)$ of a function $f: M^{2n} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the vector field metrically equivalent to the differential df . Thus

$$g(grad(f), V) = g(df, V) = df(V) = Vf \quad (5.8)$$

The Hessian of the smooth function f on M is its second covariant differential $h = \nabla(\nabla f) = \nabla^2 f$, associated with the Levi-Civita connection ∇ of g [7]. Since,

$$\nabla_V f = \nabla f(V) = df(V) = Vf \quad (5.9)$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} h(V, U) &= (\nabla(\nabla f))(V, U) = (\nabla(df))(V, U) = (\nabla_U(df))(V) \\ &= U((df)V) - (df)(\nabla_U V) \\ &= U(Vf) - (\nabla_U V)f \end{aligned} \quad (5.10)$$

Since, h is a symmetric tensor field. From (5.8), we obtain

$$(\nabla_U V)f = g(\text{grad}(f), \nabla_U V)$$

Then, from the (5.10), we have

$$h(V, U) = g(\nabla_U \text{grad}(f), V) \quad (5.11)$$

The metric defined by $h = \nabla^2 f$ is said to be pseudo-Riemannian Hessian metric if the Hessian $\nabla^2 f$ of a smooth function f associated with the metric g is non-degenerate of constant index [7].

Suppose \tilde{g} denote the twin Norden Bronze metric as given in (5.1) and (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) denote the almost complex Norden Bronze manifold. Let ∇ and $\tilde{\nabla}$ represent the Levi-Civita connections of pseudo-Riemannian metrics g and \tilde{g} , respectively. Let $f: (M^{2n}, \Psi_c, g) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a smooth function on M^{2n} then, we represent the Hessian of f by h and \tilde{h} , respectively endowed with the ∇ and $\tilde{\nabla}$ of g and \tilde{g} . Hence by equation (5.8), pseudo-Riemannian Hessian metrics on (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) are given by

$$h(U, V) = g(\nabla_U \text{grad}(f), V) \quad (5.12)$$

and

$$\tilde{h}(U, V) = \tilde{g}(\tilde{\nabla}_U \text{grad}(f), V) \quad (5.13)$$

From equations (5.2) and (5.12), we get

$$h(U, V) = \frac{6}{11} \tilde{g}(\nabla_U \text{grad}(f), V) - \frac{2}{11} \tilde{g}(\nabla_U \text{grad}(f), \Psi_c V)$$

Now, using (5.3) and (5.13), we obtain

$$h(U, V) = \frac{6}{11} \tilde{h}(U, V) - \frac{6}{11} \tilde{g}(Q(U, \text{grad}(f)), V) - \frac{2}{11} \tilde{g}(\nabla_U \text{grad}(f), \Psi_c V) \quad (5.14)$$

From (5.4), $F(U, V, W) = (\nabla_U \tilde{g})(V, W)$ this implies that

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{g}(\nabla_U \text{grad}(f), \Psi_c V) &= U \tilde{g}(\text{grad}(f), \Psi_c V) - \tilde{g}(\text{grad}(f), \nabla_U \Psi_c V) \\ &\quad - F(U, \text{grad}(f), \Psi_c V) \end{aligned} \quad (5.15)$$

Putting above equation in (5.14), then using (5.14), we have

$$\begin{aligned} h(U, V) &= \frac{6}{11} \tilde{h}(U, V) - \frac{6}{11} \tilde{g}(Q(U, \text{grad}(f)), V) - \frac{2}{11} [U \tilde{g}(\text{grad}(f), \Psi_c V) \\ &\quad - \tilde{g}(\text{grad}(f), \tilde{\nabla}_U \Psi_c V) - \tilde{g}(\text{grad}(f), Q(U, \Psi_c V)) \\ &\quad - F(U, \text{grad}(f), \Psi_c V)] \end{aligned}$$

By using (5.13) and $\tilde{\nabla} \tilde{g} = 0$, we get from the above equation

$$\begin{aligned} h(U, V) &= \frac{6}{11} \tilde{h}(U, V) - \frac{6}{11} \tilde{g}(Q(U, \text{grad}(f)), V) - \frac{2}{11} [\tilde{h}(U, \Psi_c V) \\ &\quad - \tilde{g}(\text{grad}(f), Q(U, \Psi_c V)) - F(U, \text{grad}(f), \Psi_c V)] \end{aligned} \quad (5.16)$$

The tensors F and Q vanishes for a Kaehler-Norden Bronze manifold (see remark (5.1)) then from (5.16), we have the following result:

Theorem 5.2 Let h and \tilde{h} be pseudo-Riemannian Hessian metrics and (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) be an almost

complex Norden Bronze manifold. If (M^{2n}, Ψ_c, g) is Kaehler-Norden Bronze manifold then

$$\tilde{h}(U, \Psi_c V) = 3\tilde{h}(U, V) - \frac{11}{2}h(U, V) \quad (5.17)$$

And

$$\tilde{h}(U, V) = h(U, \Psi_c V) \quad (5.18)$$

Remark 5.2 From the proposition (4.3), if the smooth function f is holomorphic then $(M^{2n}, \Psi_c, h = \nabla^2 f)$ is Kaehler-Norden Bronze Hessian manifold, i.e., $h(\Psi_c U, V) = h(U, \Psi_c V)$. So that, from the equation (5.18), we have

$$\tilde{h}(U, V) = h(\Psi_c U, V) = (h \circ \Psi_c)(U, V) \quad (5.19)$$

Therefore, equations (5.19) and (5.17) are equivalent to (5.1) and (5.2), respectively. Therefore, the Hessian metric \tilde{h} is a twin Norden Bronze Hessian metric for Kaehler-Norden Bronze Hessian manifold $(M^{2n}, \Psi_c, h = \nabla^2 f)$.

References

1. Gezer, A. N., Cengiz, Salimov, A. *On integrability of Golden Riemannian structures*, Turk. J. Math. 37, 693-703, 2013.
2. Gezer, A., Karaman, C., *Golden-Hessian structures*, Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. India A, Phys. Sci. 86, 41-46, 2016.
3. Primo, A., Reyes, E., *Some algebraic and geometric properties of the Silver number*, Mathematics and Informatics Quarterly, 18, 2007.
4. Salimov, A., Iscan, M., Etayo, F., *Paraholomorphic B-manifold and its properties*, Topology Appl. 154(4), 925, 933, 2007.
5. Salimov, A., Gezer, A., *Norden structures of Hessian type*, Turk. J. Math. 38, 462-469, 2014.
6. Hretcanu, C., Crasmareanu, M., *On some invariant submanifolds in a Riemannian manifold with golden structure*, An Stiins Univ Al I Cuza Iasi Mat (NS)., 53, 199-211, 2007.
7. Udriste, C., Bercu, G., *Riemannian Hessian metrics*, Analele Univ Bucuresti, 55(1), 189-204, 2005.
8. Bercu, G., Corcodel, C., Postolache, M., *Advances on Hessian structures*, Politehn Univ Bucharest Sci Bull Ser A Appl Math Phys 73(1), 63-70, 2011.
9. Bercu, G., Corcodel, C., Postolache, M., *The geodesics of a pseudo-Riemannian manifold*, J Adv. Math. Stud., 2(2), 9-16, 2009.
10. Bercu, G., *Pseudo-Riemannian structures with the same connection*, Balkan J. Geom. Appl., 11(1), 23-38, 2006.
11. Shima, H., *On certain locally flat homogeneous manifolds of solvable Lie groups*, Osaka J. Math., 13(2), 213-229, 1976.
12. Shima, H., Yagi, K., *Geometry of Hessian manifolds*, Diff. Geom. Appl., 7(3), 277-290, 1997.
13. Shima, H., *The geometry of Hessian structures*, World Scientific Publ. Co., Singapore, 2007.
14. Duistermaat, J. J., *On Hessian Riemannian structures*, Asian J. Math., 5(1), 79-91, 2001.
15. Yano, K., Ako, M., *On certain operators associated with tensor fields*, Kodai Math. Semin., Rep., 20, 414-436, 1968.

16. Yano, K., Kon, M., *Structures on manifolds*. Series in Pure Mathematics, 3. World Scientific Publishing Co., Singapore, 1984.
17. Crasmareanu, M., Hretcanu, C., *Golden differential geometry*, Chaos Solitons Fractals, 38(5), 1229-1238, 2008.
18. Iscan, M., Salimov, A. A., *On Kaehler-Norden manifolds*, Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. Math. Sci., 119, 71-80, 2009.
19. Ozkan, M., Peltek, B., *A new structure on manifolds: Silver structure*, International Electronic Journal of Geometry, 9 (2), 59-69, 2016.
20. Kumar, R. D., *Higher order Hessian structures on manifolds*, Proc Indian Acad. Sci. Math. Sci., 115(3), 259-277, 2005.
21. Goldberg, S. I., Yano, K., *Polynomial structures on manifolds*, Kodai Math. Sem. Rep., 22, 199-218, 1970.
22. Tachibana, S., *Analytic tensor and its generalization*, Tohoku Math. J., 12, 208-221, 1960.
23. Sameer, M., Pandey, P. K., *A Note on the silver Hessian Structure*, Journal of Science and Arts, No. 2(24), 375-388, 2024.
24. Schurman, T., *Bias analysis in entropy estimation*, J. Phys. A., 37, 295-301, 2004.
25. Pandey P. K., Sameer, *Bronze Differential Geometry*, Journal of Science and Arts, No. 4(45), 973-980, 2018.